

Challenges of the Future for Chemical Education

KRISHNA C JOSHI* and RAHUL JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 16 December 1993, revised 1 June 1995, accepted 14 December 1995

Some years back, the journal, *Nature*, in its April 12, 1984 issue, gave a vivid account of the state of science in India. One section of the report was exclusively devoted to the state of science education and on the Indian university system. The report created a furore in academic and government circles and was extensively debated. While it is true that the country has made significant progress in the field of science and technology and we are now amongst the top seven technologically advanced countries, the same cannot be said as far as the state of higher education is concerned. In the decade since 1984, the academic scenario has become more chaotic in majority of institutions. Of course, there are 'islands' of excellence but these are rather exceptions than rule. There has been an increasing deterioration in the quality of teaching and administration in the conventional universities with a tremendous increase in the number of students and decreasing funds for necessary infrastructure.

While this deterioration has pervaded all scientific disciplines, it is more than true for Chemical Education. In the second-half of this century, chemistry has made major advances on many fronts and there has been an explosion in terms of knowledge available. New theories have emerged in several areas and sophisticated instrumental techniques have been developed. Besides, far-reaching applications of chemical principles and specially structural theory have been made in areas like biological sciences, medicine, nutrition, geology, astronomy, engineering sciences etc. All this has posed serious challenges to chemical educators and they have to re-assess their role not only in the development of chemistry but also of related disciplines, technology and daily life. These challenges are outlined below.

Challenges of chemistry

Chemistry is an experimental science and unlike physics and some other scientific disciplines, the financial grant received literally goes down the drain! Referring to the financial constraints of chemistry teaching, Professor Upendra Baxi, former Vice-Chancellor of the Delhi University, remarked in a recent article in the *Hindustan Times*: "...Things have come to such a sorry pass that a leading scientist and a former Vice-Chancellor of a State university had to observe at a public meeting at Delhi University that his department was grateful (!) for a prolonged laboratory staff strike since cuts in departmental budget did not allow resources to afford the necessary costly chemicals for practical examination".

Chemistry is increasing in the volume of contents as well as in the scope and level of the mathematical formulations of the chemical concepts. A mere look at the increasing size and cost of *Chemical Abstracts* is enough to con-

vince one of this explosion. Millions of chemical compounds are already reported and about fifty thousand are in use. It took about 32 years to make the first million entries in the *Chemical Abstracts* but now one million publications are reported in less than two years. Yet it will be interesting to find out how many departments of chemistry in our colleges and universities are able to subscribe to *Chemical Abstracts*.

To cope with the tremendous increase in chemical information, we need a substantial increase in funds just to get this information. Our libraries are totally inadequate and cannot subscribe even to the basic and classical journals—not to speak of specialised ones. To a great majority of chemists, there is no way to get this information except to get some from INSDOC in a limited way.

Challenges of Society

The present-day emphasis is on the relevance of the research to the needs of the society. The human resources of our country arise from our stock of teachers and scientists-based in more than two hundred institutions of higher learning and nearly seven thousand colleges. In a way, they will be accountable for both the destruction of science and scientific temper in India as well as progress in this field.

In view of a tremendous growth of population and change in the standards of living, it is necessary to ponder over the type of education we are giving to our students and to consider what kind of chemistry will serve the changing needs of the society. One will find the chemists working in all sorts of profession today. They are working in the chemical and pharmaceutical industry, in agriculture and food industry, in paper, rubber and plastic productions, in metallurgy and construction materials, energy production, in mechanical, electronics, aerospace industries and even in hotels, commerce, banking, transport and administration. This diversity of the work of a chemist leaves a chemical educator in great dilemma about how to teach the subject satisfying such diverse needs.

For a teacher to do his job well, it is necessary that the mafia culture pervading our universities should go and those who claim to provide academic leadership, should devote more time to their classes and the laboratories and not function solely as 'Airport Scientists'.

Challenges of the individual

The factors mentioned above create a situation in which constant improvement and innovation in methods of chemical education are needed and in this difficult task, success can be achieved only if we have well-prepared and motivated teachers. The rising scientific level of the chemical sciences puts high demand for abstract reasoning in students and this needs teachers of excellence. Thus, the na-

ture of a chemistry teacher's job is increasingly becoming more challenging and requires more ingenuity.

For an individual teacher, chemistry is not merely knowledge of facts and theories. In a situation where knowledge is rapidly becoming obsolete, it is equally important that the method of acquiring and validating fresh knowledge should be encouraged. The broader objectives of a good teaching are also development of all mental faculties, related skills and developing right attitudes. Our society is getting transformed from traditional to a more modern society. Therefore, a chemistry teacher is expected to take advantage of recent developments in educational technology—the audio and visual components, the opportunities of self-learning and distance education and the immense potentiality of the computers.

Problems of curriculum development

In the 1960's, chemistry courses were drastically changed in most of the western countries—both in contents as well as on emphasis. There was a transition from descriptive type of chemistry to theoretical and general chemistry. Quite often, the change was too drastic leading to funny situations in the classroom when an advanced student did not know if barium sulphate was a solid or a gas! In the January 1988 issue of *Chemistry in Britain*, an interesting article appeared on 'Recruitment of Chemists' and it narrated the experience of interviewing 'Oxbridge' graduates when it was noticed that majority of them could not write the formula for phenol. It was then felt that a logical and rational development between theory and experimental should be retained. At any time, curriculum development is a complicated job. It involves a broad concept and has to take into consideration the rapid expansion of the subject, its diversification as well as development of human resources for different national tasks. At present, there is a general apathy of students to a serious study of the subject. Some of the reasons for this are as follows: (i) For the great majority of the students, chemistry as a subject is of only terminal interest. (ii) In a given class-room, only a small minority of students is fascinated by knowledge. Such students are not given any separate chance of learning. (iii) Students are not encouraged to learn in a more organised and independent way. (iv) There is a lack of innovative curricula. The laboratory syllabus is unexciting. (v) Library facilities are inadequate and students are not encouraged to use whatever library facilities are available. (vi) There is a lack of visual resource material. (vii) The evaluation/examination system has lost its credibility. (viii) With some honourable exceptions, teachers, as a community, do not inspire students.

Therefore, any exercise in curriculum development should be able to devise, plan and implement a course of study taking into account the variations in student background, knowledge, skills and needs. Besides, due to the vastness of the country, there is great variation in the calibre of students and quality of teaching from place to place. Although there are some very good institutions with brilliant students, these are engulfed in a quagmire of mediocrity.

Some years back, the University Grants Commission undertook an exercise in framing a syllabus for chemistry students both at the undergraduate and post-graduate levels. The present author (K.C.J.) had the privilege of being the Coordinator of the Curriculum Development Centre and a report was submitted to the U.G.C. in June 1988. The C.D.C. included eminent university and college teachers, representatives from industries, commercial organisations, Government departments and research institutes. It was one of the most extensive exercise done so far in the country. The tasks assigned to the Centre were: (i) modernisation of the existing syllabi and courses, (ii) developing alternative models, (iii) preparing necessary textual material and other supporting materials and (iv) imparting necessary training to the teachers.

The C.D.C. prepared a 'model' syllabus which is quite flexible so that different institutions can adapt it to suit their needs. A major recommendation is that chemistry teaching has to be integrated with related scientific disciplines like mathematics, biology, electronics and computer science. Most of the interesting chemistry at present is being done at the cell level and needs an integrated knowledge. Computers are being increasingly used in diverse field like evaluating medicinal compounds (QSAR) and planning synthesis of novel systems. Keeping such trends in view, the C.D.C. planned, besides 'Core' papers, a number of 'Elective' papers which should be available to the students depending upon local conditions and the aptitude of students. It is gratifying to note that a number of institutions have taken advantage of this report and updated their curriculum suitably.

The University Grants Commission's scheme of Refresher Courses for college teachers was sound in principle as far as updating the knowledge of teachers is concerned. It is yet to be assessed how far it has served its aim. There are already whispers about the quality of faculty members in many of these courses. The U.G.C. should set up some machinery to evaluate the performance of these Workshops.

It will be appropriate, in conclusion, to quote from the words of a leading chemical educator, Professor Aleksandra Kornhauser, Director, International Centre for Chemical Studies, Ljubljana, former Yugoslavia:

".....Next to the needs of society and the growing field of chemistry, chemistry teaching has also to cope with the problems of the individual. Chemistry is not easy to learn and consequently not easy to teach. The "alphabet of chemistry", i.e. the minimum "critical knowledge" of facts and theories needed for basic understanding of this discipline is extensive. Abstract concepts and the use of mathematics make it more demanding to study. Another pre-requisite is the precise work expected in the laboratory. The enrolment in chemistry is often low and even some chemists think that we could and should not do anything about this phenomenon forgetting that chemistry is really necessary if we are to solve society's problems.....".